

Smart herbal assistance for health care

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Abstract— An important part of maintaining both mental and physical well-being is through the use of ayurvedic medicines. The study will employ deep learning techniques to recognise regional kinds of the herbal plants. The plan has a high level of social relevance because it would address the issues of numerous stakeholders, including doctors, pharmacists, the government, and the general public. A considerable impact on medical and other relevant research may be from the identification of uncommon plant species. Identification of plant species in isolated and forested places, where humans have limited access, is an additional potential use. We need prior exposure to the plant in order to learn about it and its medical properties. Since they are unaware of these plants before, some people may find the process tiresome. result 28 Additionally, occasions there are when we must rely on others to identify therapeutic plants. i.e., botanists and knowledgeable individuals. Therefore, using current technology and computer devices, we developed a model (Deep Neural Networks) for the identification of medicinal plants in order to avoid all of these kinds of circumstances.

Keywords— Convolution neural network, Deep learning, ResNet50, Database, GUI

I. INTRODUCTION

An old branch of medicine known as Ayurveda collaborates with medicinal herbs. Ayurveda dates back to 6000 BC, when it first spread orally from person to person because there was no document format. Ayurvedic concepts date back to technological sophistication, breadth, reliability, and universality. Machine learning can be applied 4 in Ayurveda e-commerce to increase user experiences and extend the market because the of Ayurvedic medicine is widely accessible, more affordable, and has less negative effects. It system 25 the Indus Valley Civilization, which existed around 330 BC. The Vedas, which are found in Atharvaveda, are where Ayurveda's first recorded forms of medicine emerged. Ayurvedic medicine uses roots and naturally occurring plants as its constituents. The accurate identification of plants is crucial in Ayurveda. 27 People who are unfamiliar uses collect them with the plants and their for the purpose 3 medicines; if they mix one plant with another that is identical when collecting, an adverse effect will result. Finding the right medicinal herbs to treat this scenario is a crucial effort. We've included a capability to acquire a description of the plant's therapeutic properties in this system. of making Artificial intelligence and machine learning are important in the modern world. The use of technology is expanding along with its sophistication as time goes on. This technology reduces costs and does many other things. Physical, mental, and emotional situations could be reliably anticipated utilizing heartbeat diagnostics. And the imbalance in the tridoshas made diseases easy to predict. In recent years, the combination of machine learning and ayurveda has increased the latter's can also be utilised to improve economic big impact on applications that have a cost savings, revenue growth, and utilisation. This document is a template. For questions on paper guidelines, please contact us via e-mail.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In [1], Herbal plants are classified in this study of research as those that can be utilised as an alternative to traditional medical treatment to treat illnesses. The majority of people are still clueless that there are herbal plants because there are so many diverse types, identifying medicinal plants takes expert knowledge. Few of them are shown in Figures 1,2 & 3. They employed long short-term recall (CNN-LSTM) and convolutional neural network techniques. Nine different types of leaves from herbs were separated into training and testing samples for the sake of identification. In this study, plants were identified using convolutional neural networks, and the estimated accuracy of recognising them was calculated using a similar method. In [2], it claims that the discovery of rare plant species may have a substantial influence on future medical and related studies. For the task of identifying leaves, the effectiveness of the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and the pretrained models VGG16 and VGG19 have been examined. The dataset includes pictures of 64 medicinal plants' leaves. A classification

accuracy of 98.79% was attained by CNN. VGG16 and VGG19 surpass standard CNN with accuracy rates of 97.8% and 97.6%, respectively. We learned that CNN can be used for more accurate reporting.

In [3], The paper discusses the diseases that plants can treat, along with information on their medical properties. By classifying the plant based on its characteristics, it will help us in determining the medical benefits that specific plant provides. The take away that we learnt was that it is possible to forecast medical qualities and treatable disorders.

In [4], The study presented here suggests a computerised system for classifying plant species by looking at digital images of their leaves. For this recognition, they are using common knowledge that has been passed down from earlier generations. A number of approaches have been put forth for the automated analysis of plant leaves. The suggested approach combines SURF and HOG characteristics that were taken from photos of leaves and classifies them using a k-NN classifier.

In [5], this study claims that considerable preprocessing is necessary before classifying plant species based on their leaves. Separating the leaf from the background, where the lighting is unreliable, is the first stage. The segmented leaf is then used to extract features based on colour and texture. The third and last stage is to classify the plant species using the traits that were previously retrieved. To medicinal plant, a classifier based on logistic regression is applied. Authors in [6] have addressed the various classifiers at different applications. The multinomial logistic regression model has been added to the binary logistic regression model since the suggested approach relies on the categorization of many classes. The multinomial logic is used to compare different groups by combining binary logistic regressions. As a result it is possible to compare each obtained label category to a reference category in the dataset.

Fig 1- Aloe Vera

Fig 2- Tulsi

Fig 3- Hibiscus

III.METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. Dataset for Medicinal Plants

Authors in [7] have highlighted the significance of the right medicinal plants through identification of the shape, size and colour using image processing techniques .The database of medicinal plants has 14502 photos broken down into 11 species-based groups. Aloe vera, Ashwagandha, Banana, Bhringraj, Cactus, Cissus quadrangularis, Hibiscus, Mexican mint, Mint and Tulsi are one of the 11 main folders in our

dataset. The images were split and resized to make the leaf cover the majority of the space. We also inverted photos vertically and horizontally to improve our accuracy.

As a result, our dataset grows in size and we have picture data. Resnet50 architecture is used for image more distinctive test subjects for our model. The identification dataset is divided into both training and testing subsets, and we use 80–85 percent of the photographs in the learning sample to develop our model. Using the validation subset, we assess performance as well as training ages as well as validation losses. To subject any image for further analysis Preprocessing is a very important phase. The significance of the extraction and preprocessing are understood through [10].

After getting the real time dataset the following tasks were performed:

Image extraction

The background data of the leaf image data is removed during this stage to reveal the actual leaf image data.

Image Pre-processing:

The image is changed to a greyscale version at this step, the noise in the processing leaf data is eliminated, and any distortions in the image are also addressed using geometric transformations including translation, rotation, and scaling

B. RESNET50 Architecture

Residual Network is referred to as ResNet. They comprise mainly can be downloaded and configured according to user- provided parameters. These networks have many iterations and models that are set up in advance and can be downloaded. A convolutional neural network, or CNN, with 50 layers is called ResNet-50. Using ResNet 50 along with CNN can give a better accuracy for the image classification process [9]. A common neural network system that serves as the foundation for many computer vision applications is called ResNet, short for Residual Networks. ResNet's key innovation was its ability to train extremely complex artificial neural networks layers in total. For the purpose with over 150 of accurately labelling images, neural networks using convolution are developed. CNN 26 performs best when dealing with picture data. Resnet50 architecture indicated in Figure 5 is used for image identification.

The architecture comprises of

- A convolution with 64 distinct kernels, each with a stride of size 2 and a kernel size of 7×7 results in 1 layer.

- Following that, we witness max pooling with a stride size of 2.

- In the next convolution there is a $1 \times 1, 64$ kernel following this a $3 \times 3, 64$ kernel and at last a $1 \times 1, 256$ kernel, these three layers are repeated in total 3 time so giving us 9 layers in this step.

- The kernel of $1 \times 1, 128$ is next, followed by the kernel of $3 \times 3, 128$ and, finally, the kernel of $1 \times 1, 512$.
2 times

We performed this procedure four for a total of 12 layers.

- Next to that, we have $1 \times 1, 256$, a kernel with a followed by t size wo more of kernels with sizes of $3 \times 3, 256$ and $1 \times 1, 1024$, repeated six times which are to give us a total of 18 layers.

Fig 4-Skip Correction

Fig 5- Res Net 50 Model Architecture

Fig 6-Architecture of CNN

Then, a $1 \times 1,512$ kernel was added, followed by two more kernels of $3 \times 3,512$ and $1 \times 1,2048$. This process was repeated three times giving us a total of 9 layers.

Following that, we perform an average pool, finishing with fully connected layer made up of 1000 nodes and a Softmax function to give us one layer.

Reasons for having these layers and features in architecture:

- CNN stands for Convolutional Neural Network and belongs to the Deep Neural Network family. The significance of CNN in the field of image classification is expressed in [8]. The architecture of CNN is as indicated in Figure 6. It is mostly utilized in Computer vision (CV) to identify patterns present in the subject object. Finding patterns in input data and predicting them is CNN's primary goal. It offers increased performance and higher accuracy.

C. Layers in CNN:

A crucial and essential component of a convolutional neural network is the convolutional layer. There are several self-learnable filters in ConvNet.

ReLU stands for Rectified Linear Unit. ReLU is an Activation Function. The given input matrices are reduced in dimension using the pooling layer. There are three types: Minimum, Maximum, and Average pooling. There are numerous nodes (neurons) connect the Fully Connected Layer.

- **Stride:** In convolution, the quantity of movement is referred to as stride. The default value is one. The filters are moved to 1 pixel at a time when stride=1.

Padding: Padding aids in maintaining the input's original proportions. In this case the zeroes are added to the inputs externally, The size of the kernel affects the number of zero layers used.

- **ReLU Function:** Following the convolutional layer is the activation function. Here, the activation function is the Rectified Linear Unit. If the input is positive, the function returns that value; else, it returns 0 i.e., $R(z) = \max(0, z)$. **Dropout:** The CNN feature "Dropout" is employed frequently. This could be the outcome of the overfitting issue in our model by randomly deleting some of the connections already exist between the nodes.

- **Image augmentation:**

Using Python programming, augmentation is carried out. As a result, the photographs may change in accordance with the predetermined category of size-valued attributes. So that the can learn how to see the images from various angles. **Pooling Layer:** Dimensionality is decreased through pooling. By lowering model the number of parameters, it cuts training time in half and prevents overfitting. Preserving vital data when pooling layers down sample on each feature map independently. Additionally, the information received from the previous layer is summarized in this layer. A window is dragged across the input in this instance of max pooling, which takes the maximum value in the pooling window. There aren't any parameters for pooling.

Fully Connected Layer (FC): Include fully connected layers after convolution and pooling layers. Weights, biases, and neurons are all present in this layer. Neurons in one will be linked to neurons in another layer. By training, it is able to classify photos into many categories. The output of the last pooling layer is flattened to a vector because connected layer demands a 1D vector of numbers as its input. This vector then serves as the input to the fully connected layer.

- **Softmax Layer:** This layer is the topmost one. For multi-classification, Softmax is used. The softmax classification layer, also referred to as the softmax function, is fully connected to the final fully connected layer and produces the projected probability of each group. Multi-class sigmoids make up softmax functions. They are employed in calculating the simultaneous probabilities of several classes.

Prediction

According to the potential that the image will be classified, a function that accepts an image as input is defined. The medicinal image's name is specified. **Database Creation** A database is created to store the properties and the diseases that can be cured for each medicinal plant that are identified using ResNet50 architecture.

GUI Interfacing

A graphical user interface GUI, is an user interface with electronic that devices computers and smartphones by using menus, icons, and other visual cues (graphics). Unlike text-based interfaces, where data and commands are purely in text, GUIs graphically show information and related user

controls. A pointing device, such as a mouse, trackball, stylus, or a finger on a touch screen, is used to manipulate GUI representations. Gradio was utilized in this instance for the GUI.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The definition of a function includes an argument for the image path. This image is being loaded into PIL format. This is done because the image we use may be in a JPG or PNG format thus we are utilizing the PIL format to standardize and interact with all image formats. The PIL Image instance is resized to (255,255) and transformed to a Numpy array. We added a new axis, and now we compute in the y direction using the image array. Using the model.predict() method of keras, we can determine the class for this new image. Class indices ultimately will emerge from this. The corresponding medicinal properties of a class will be anticipated based on the likelihood of the class indices. A GUI will be used to display this medicinal value.

Fig7-Accuracy Plot

The plot in Figure 7 shows maximum training accuracy is 87.7% and validation accuracy is 95% for epochs of 3. As we can see from graph, accuracy increases with number of epochs.

Fig.8 —Loss plot

As we can see in Figure 8, training loss and accuracy loss decreases as the number of epochs increases.

GUI output

Figures 9,10,11 are the outputs shown with the help of GUI along With the medicinal properties of Tulsi, Aloe vera and Hibiscus plants respectively. The model was tested for the images of these plants.

Fig. 9—GUI output of Tulsi

Fig. 10—GUI output of Aloe vera

Fig. 11—GUI output of Hibiscus

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposed and applied a method for automatically recognising plants for medicinal purposes from their leaves. The proposed deep system uses learning methods and the ResNet50 model architecture to distinguish an already trained medicinal herb from its leaf. A database is created to keep track of the traits and diseases it can treat. Additionally, a graphical user interface is developed to display the outcome depending on the supplied image. This recommended approach can therefore address current problems including the reliance on traditional methods, the accuracy level's ongoing discontent, and the demand for herbal plant identification experts.

VI. FUTURE WORK

To increase the size of the samples as well the dataset by increasing the as by adding new kinds of medicinal plants. Object recognition from videos also recommended. That is when a video is given as input, it can identify various medicinal plants in the video.

REFERENCES

- [1] Haryono, Khairul Anam, Azmi Saleh, "Novel Herbal Leaf Identification and Authentication Using Deep Learning Neural Network," IEEE, May 14, 2021
- [2] AnuPaulson, Ravishankar S, "AI based indigenous medicinal plant identification", IEEE, Oct 24, 2020.
- [3] C Amuthalingeswaran, M Sivakumar, Dr P Renuga, S Alexpandi, "Identification of medicinal plants and their usage by using deep learning", IEEE, Vol-7 Issue-4 2021.
- [4] Amala Sabu, Sreekumar K, Rahul R Nair, "Recognition of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants from Leaves: A Computer Vision Approach," IEEE, March 12, 2018
- [5] CSivaranjani, Lekshmi Kalinathan, R. Amutha Ruba Soundar Kathavarayan, K.J. Jegadish Kumar, "Real-Time Identification of Medicinal Plants using Techniques," IEEE, October 11, 2019.
- [6] Konovalenko I, Maruschak P, Brevus V & Prentkovskis O, "Recognition of scratches and abrasions on metal surfaces using a classifier based on a convolutional neural network", Metals, 11(4) met11040549 (2021) 549, <https://doi.org/10.3390/>
- [7] P. Manoj Kumar; C. M. Surya; Varun P. Gopi. "Identification of ayurvedic medicinal plants by image processing of leaf samples" IEEE ICRCICN 2017
- [8] Muthukrishnan Ramprasath, Shanmugasundaram Hariharan et al. "Image Classification using Convolutional Neural Networks" International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics 2018
- [9] Sanjay A. Agrawal, Vaibhav D. Rewaskar, Rucha A. Agrawal et al, "Advancements in NSFW Content Detection: A Comprehensive Review of ResNet-50 Based Approaches "International Journal of intelligent systems and applications in engineering.2023
- [10] Massimo Salvi, U. Rajendra Acharya "The impact of pre- and post-image processing techniques on deep learning frameworks: A comprehensive review for digital pathology image analysis" Computers in Biology and Medicine-Jan 2021